

A MOBILE APP FOR WIFI ATTENDANCE SYSTEM

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Abstract: An attendance system is a crucial aspect of any organization, enabling efficient tracking of employees' attendance and punctuality. With the advancement of technology, traditional attendance systems have been replaced by modern, automated systems. One such system is the Wi-fi Attendance System, which employs wireless communication technology to record and manage employee attendance. This system utilizes Wi-fi-enabled devices, such as smartphones, tablets, or laptops, to connect with a central server and log attendance information. The system offers several benefits, such as real-time attendance monitoring, accurate and reliable data recording, and the ability to generate reports and analytics. This abstract provides an overview of the Wi-fi Attendance System and highlights its importance in modern-day attendance management."

Keywords: Wi-fi , Attendance , Technology.

Introduction: Attendance tracking is a fundamental component of effective workforce management in any organization. Traditionally, attendance management systems required manual data entry, which was a tedious and error-prone process. However, with technological advancements, automated attendance systems have become increasingly popular. One such system is the Wi-fi Attendance System, which utilizes wireless communication technology to track employee attendance. The system relies on Wi-fi enabled devices to connect to a central server and record attendance data. This system offers several advantages over traditional attendance systems, such as real-time attendance monitoring, automatic data recording, and the ability to generate detailed reports and analytics. In this introduction, we will explore the Wi-fi Attendance System in-depth and discuss its benefits, limitations, and potential impact on workforce management."

Existing system: In the present system all attendance work is done on paper format. The whole session attendance is stored in register and at the end of the session the reports are generated. Making manual attendance is more tedious process. It takes lot of time for recording data. Paper work on the other hand is a cumbersome process. There are chances for errors and also updating of data is difficult. Another important drawback of existing system is time factor. It will not help the staff to provide the information in time.

Language Specification :

Android: Android is an open source and Linux-based Operating System for mobile devices such as smart phones and tablet computers. Android was developed by the Open Handset Alliance, led by Google, and other companies. Android offers a unified approach to application development for mobile devices which means developers need only develop for Android, and their applications should be able to run on different devices powered by Android.

SQLite Features:

- SQLite is totally free: SQLite is open-source. So, no license is required to work with it.
- SQLite is serverless: SQLite doesn't require a different server process or system to operate.
- SQLite is very flexible: It facilitates you to work on multiple databases on the same session on the same time.
- Configuration Not Required: SQLite doesn't require configuration. No setup or administration required.
- SQLite is a cross-platform DBMS: You don't need a large range of different platforms like Windows, Mac OS, Linux, and Unix. It can also be used on a lot of embedded operating systems like Symbian, and Windows CE.
- Storing data is easy: SQLite provides an efficient way to store data.
- Variable length of columns: The length of the columns is variable and is not fixed. It facilitates you to allocate only the space a field needs. For example, if you have a varchar (200) column, and you put a 10 characters' length value on it, then SQLite will allocate only 10 characters' space for that value not the whole 200 space.
- Provide large number of API's: SQLite provides API for a large range of programming languages. For example: .Net languages (Visual Basic, C#), PHP, Java, Objective C, Python and a lot of other programming language.

Data Flow Diagram: DFD depict hoe data interact with the system. DFD are extremely useful in modelling many aspects of a business function because they systematically subdivide a task into basic parts, helping the analyst understand the system that they trying to model data flow diagram models a system by using external entities from which data flow to a process.

- Represents a process

- Which shows data flow

- Designation of the data

- Shows Data source

Architecture diagram:

Disadvantage:

- Not User Friendly
- Difficulty in report generation
- Manual control
- Lots of paperwork
- Time consuming

Advantage:

- This system is to provide a user-friendly application.
- This application automatically fetches student Wi-Fi information.
- Based on the Wi-Fi list the staff can make the attendance.
- No time-consuming process.
- This proposed system eliminates the use of paperwork needed for attendance marking and monitoring.

Feasibility Study: A system is a feasible system only if it is feasible within limited recourse and time. In this system each and every process can be feasible for the user and also developer. It proved user friendly input such as device independent inputs and getting proper solution for the problem.

Technical Feasibility: Technical Feasibility is the assessment of the technical view of the system. The system is developed for Dot net environment; a platform independent tool is used to develop the system.

Behavioural Feasibility: It is common knowledge that computers illustrations have something to do with turnover transfers, retraining and changes in user or developer status.

Operational Feasibility: Operational Feasibility deals with the study of prospects of the system. This system operationally eliminates all the tensions of the administrator and helps in effectively tracking the project progress.

Wi-Fi Name Detection: In this module staff login this application using their user name and password. After successful login the user find the Wi-Fi names to using this application.

Name Selection: After finding the Wi-Fi names the staff can select the particular student name to this application. This all the process will be stored in a separate table.

Attendance Marking: In this module staff search and find the Wi-Fi name after that they can detect the student name and marking the attendance using this application. This information will be stored in separate table.

Data flow Diagram

Level-0

Login, Enter staff entry

Login, put attendance based on

Level 1

Level 2: User

Ex Diagram

Conclusion: Implementation is the stage of the project when the theoretical design is turned out into a working system. Thus, it can be considered to be the most critical stage in achieving a successful new system and in giving the user, confidence that the new system will work and be effective. The application can be used to manage the data of all type of educational institutes.

Websites:

- <http://www.onjava.com>
- <http://java.sun.com>
- <http://www.java.net>
- <https://www.ibm.com>